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Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the U2Demo¹ project. Views and opinions expressed in this document are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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¹ <https://u2demo.eu/>

Executive Summary

The Deliverable Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan (D7.1) outlines U2Demo's **communication strategy and activities**. It will include at least two versions, with the first submitted at M6 and updated at M24 (or earlier if justified). This deliverable has been prepared by the leader of Work Package WP7 – **REScoop.Vlaanderen**.

The **U2Demo Project**, launched in **September 2024** with €5 million in funding under the **Horizon Europe** framework, aims to revolutionize energy distribution and democratize access to sustainable energy through **Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading** and **Energy Sharing**. The project focuses on developing consumer-centered management strategies to enable widespread participation in decentralized energy systems.

To **ensure the project's success and impact**, its strategies and solutions must be effectively communicated and disseminated to relevant target groups during the project lifespan and beyond. To this end, the D&C Plan identifies the **key target audiences** mentioned in the project proposal and outlines the **communication and dissemination strategies** needed to share the project's main goals and outcomes.

This deliverable builds upon the preliminary dissemination and communication plan, agreed upon by the consortium and outlined in the U2Demo grant agreement, with additional details and structure. The document presents an **overview of U2Demo's target audiences and key messages while detailing the project's communication channels and tools**. It also highlights the work completed in the project's first semester, including **establishing the project's visual identity** (logo and brand guidelines), creating **branded materials** (templates, headers, flyers, roll-ups, etc.), launching its **online presence** (website and social media platforms), and planning initial **dissemination activities**.

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Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ECs	Energy Communities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
P2P	Peer-to-peer
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The document “**D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan**” is the first deliverable for dissemination and communication (D&C) under **Work Package 7 (WP7)** of the **U2Demo** project. This work package focuses on developing communication and dissemination strategies to **enhance the project’s visibility** using key messages and effective communication channels; to **foster knowledge sharing** and build connections with other projects, as well as national and European initiatives; and to **assess and demonstrate the scalability and replicability** of P2P trading and energy-sharing methods, paving the way for broader adoption. Finally, WP7 is meant to ensure the project’s success by **evaluating the impact, adoption, and maintenance of open-source tools**.

According to the [Horizon Europe Work Programme](#), **communication** is the act of informing the target audiences about the vision, goals, activities, and results of the project; and **dissemination** is the act of making the research and scientific and technological knowledge available to potential users, relying strongly on the principle of open science.

According to the Grant Agreement, the **U2Demo D&C’s main strategic goals are:**

- **Developing a Dissemination & Communication Plan**, detailing target audiences, dissemination channels, and activity monitoring through KPIs.
- **Creating a cohesive U2Demo visual identity**, including a logo, templates, and promotional materials.
- **Establishing an informative project website** and maintaining active **social media** channels.
- **Producing content**, like newsletters, press releases, and videos to engage stakeholders.
- **Sharing results** with stakeholders via:
 - Publishing in open science journals;
 - Participation in conferences, workshops, and webinars;
 - Engaging in standardization initiatives;
 - Organizing project-specific events.
- **Collaborating with CINEA on Horizon Europe dissemination activities** to enhance visibility and synergies.

The goal is to **maximize the project’s visibility and impact**, ensuring its findings and tools are widely utilized.

The implementation of these activities will actively involve **consortium partners and key stakeholders** throughout the various phases of the project, strongly relying on their commitment to carry out the actions described in this deliverable. Due to the multidisciplinary

consortium, with 16 beneficiary partners and 2 affiliated partners in 8 Countries, U2Demo is in a great position to **reach a multitude of audiences and influence decisions, behaviours, and strategies** towards P2P energy sharing solutions adoption.

In addition, most U2Demo partners have well-established **networks in specific fields** and will be key in reaching out to specific target groups. Therefore, all **partners** should be committed to carrying out the proposed activities to **influence relevant audiences**.

Under the Grant Agreement, the different phases of the dissemination approach have been defined and are outlined in Figure 1. Each phase will target a different audience and be tailored according to the dissemination objectives, channels, and tools. The plan will be refined and updated throughout the project life cycle to reflect the project's progress and new opportunities considered.

WP7 Timeline – Dissemination and Communication plan

Figure 1 - U2Demo C&D Approach

The dissemination activities will continue after the end of the project to guarantee sustainability of results and impact of the project.

All D&C activities must be communicated to the U2Demo Coordination Team, responsible for leading, managing and keeping a record of all WP7 actions. The initial identification of the U2Demo target groups, as well as the dissemination and communication activities, are summarized below.

1.2 Structure

The current document is divided into 6 sections plus two annexes. Section 1 introduces and describes the deliverable. Section 2 presents the U2Demo target audiences and respective key messages. Section 3 describes the communication channels and tools. Section 4 identifies the dissemination activities. Section 5 describes how to evaluate and monitor communication and dissemination activities. Section 6 presents overall conclusions and considerations about this deliverable.

Finally, ANNEX I and ANNEX II sections show the standard brand guidelines and the U2Demo power point template, respectively.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

This deliverable is **transversal** to all activities executed within all WPs of the project, in particular to those related to the demonstration cases. The main D&C activities are managed by the WP7 **Coordination team at REScoop.Vlaanderen with the support of the coordination team at INESC ID** and will be further detailed in this document. Therefore, it is essential to foster the engagement and participation of all WP and task leaders, to support the disclosure of the D&C activities. An updated plan will be submitted at M24 (Deliverable D7.2), or earlier if changes are applied.

2 Target Audiences

The U2Demo project introduces a transformative approach to sustainable energy systems by enabling peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and energy-sharing mechanisms among active consumers and energy communities (ECs). Moving beyond traditional grid-dependent structures, U2Demo promotes a **decentralized, consumer-driven energy model** that empowers individuals and communities to directly trade and share energy in a secure, transparent, and efficient manner.

At the core of its innovation, U2Demo integrates blockchain-based transparency, adaptive market mechanisms, and AI-driven forecasting, ensuring real-time, optimized energy exchanges within local energy networks. By prioritizing open-source tools and interoperable platforms, the project provides **scalable and adaptable solutions that can be implemented across diverse regulatory and technical landscapes in Europe**.

With a strong focus on scalability, replicability, and interoperability, U2Demo is set to redefine how energy is shared, managed, and consumed, fostering a more flexible, resilient, and sustainable energy ecosystem. By leveraging smart energy solutions and cross-sector collaboration, the project aims to **empower communities and accelerate the transition** toward a clean and efficient energy future.

The project consortium will establish **comprehensive guidelines and frameworks to test, validate, and demonstrate the feasibility, cost-effectiveness, and societal impact of P2P trading and energy sharing**. These guidelines will include technical standards for interoperability, regulatory and market integration roadmaps, and best practices for governance models within ECs. Additionally, they will outline data management protocols, cybersecurity measures, and decision-support tools to ensure secure, transparent, and efficient energy transactions.

These activities will be carried out through **four demonstration sites (Pilots) across Europe**, showcasing innovative tools, methodologies, and business models designed for replication and scalability. The ultimate goal is to propose practical strategies for widespread adoption and to position U2Demo as a benchmark for sustainable energy practices in Europe.

For the successful implementation of U2Demo, it is crucial to engage and inform diverse stakeholders about the project's vision, strategies, and solutions. Target audiences include:

- **Citizens and energy communities (ECs):** Encouraging individuals and communities to participate as active consumers or prosumers in P2P trading and energy sharing.
- **Industries and businesses:** Supporting the adoption of innovative energy practices in industrial settings and showcasing cost-effective solutions for energy management.

- **Governments and policy makers:** Providing evidence-based policy recommendations to foster regulatory environments that support energy sharing and collaboration.
- **Academia and research Institutions:** Collaborating on innovation, research, and knowledge-sharing to advance smart energy systems.
- **Standardization bodies:** Ensuring interoperability and compliance with international standards for scalable energy solutions.

U2Demo's communication strategies will operate on **two levels** to maximize its impact:

A. Local/National-Targeted Communication

The project will focus on the countries hosting the demonstrators and key partners, ensuring local engagement and value creation. These efforts include:

- **Demonstration Sites/Pilots:** Countries hosting demonstration sites and pilots (Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, Portugal) will have targeted communication initiatives, including workshops, events, and stakeholder engagements.
- **Local Stakeholders:** Communication efforts will target local citizens, municipalities, national businesses, industries, and governments to raise awareness and encourage participation.
- **Key Message:** U2Demo promotes greener, more efficient, and community-driven energy solutions to transform energy-sharing practices.

B. Europe-Wide and International Communication

Beyond local efforts, U2Demo aims to have a broad impact on energy systems across Europe and globally by:

- **Highlighting** the replicability and scalability of the developed tools and methods.
- **Promoting** open-source solutions to foster collaboration and innovation.
- **Engaging** with European and international stakeholders through conferences, workshops, and partnerships.

Broader Impact

U2Demo is expected to reshape the energy sector by validating the technical and economic feasibility of P2P trading and energy sharing. By integrating local efforts with a broader European perspective, the project will build a strong network, generate new opportunities, and inspire action toward more sustainable energy systems. These efforts will ensure that U2Demo leaves a lasting impact on both local communities and the global energy landscape.

The U2Demo project brings together a consortium of 17 partners and 2 associated partners from 8 European countries, all committed to actively contributing to communication and

dissemination activities. Most of these partners are well-established institutions with dedicated communication departments and officers, enabling a strong collaborative effort to enhance the visibility of U2Demo. The U2DEMO Communication team at RESCOOP will try to work closely with partners to ensure strategic alignment and maximize outreach.

As an example, following the Kick-Off Meeting, a press release and a news article were published on the project's website and distributed to all partners, requesting their support in disseminating the information through their respective channels. This initiative has already resulted in eight articles being published across partners' websites, demonstrating the effectiveness of leveraging the consortium's communication network.

Using this approach to actively involve U2Demo partners and their networks in Communication activities, will help to scale up the project's outreach and amplify U2Demo's visibility.

Support materials for local/national communication: All communication materials developed within the U2Demo project will be written in English to ensure consistency. However, materials such as flyers, rollups, newsletters, and videos can be adapted into the partners' local languages to engage more effectively with local communities. The materials developed are already available on the [U2Demo website](#) and will be updated as new content is created. These materials will be distributed at local events and conferences. This localized approach will ensure that U2Demo's vision and solutions reach local stakeholders, fostering engagement and creating value within regional contexts.

European/international-targeted communication: U2Demo will direct its communication efforts toward European institutions (e.g., the European Commission), as well as global audiences in the energy sector and policymaking circles. The project's communication will target citizens, industries, and policymakers to promote collaboration and knowledge transfer across Europe and beyond. A general key message will be reinforced that U2Demo will deliver innovative tools, services, and business models that facilitate the adoption of peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and energy-sharing solutions. By doing so, U2Demo aims to empower energy communities and active consumers while advancing sustainable and community-driven energy systems.

Strategies for international communication: To engage a wider audience, all core materials developed in the context of U2Demo will be produced in English. U2Demo partners will participate in international conferences, liaison events (see section 4.2), and other initiatives, such as issuing press releases and media articles in international newspapers and magazines. Project results will be published in peer-reviewed international journals, further increasing the visibility and impact of the project.

Strategies for joint collaboration with peer projects: U2Demo will actively identify potential collaboration networks with other Horizon Europe peer projects. To achieve this, the project will assess available communication channels and collaboration platforms, organizing cluster meetings when relevant. The coordination team will explore the possibility of creating cross-project working groups to promote shared objectives and enhance synergies. Additionally, joint

workshops and events will be organized to facilitate knowledge exchange and networking opportunities. These collaborative efforts will amplify the project’s impact and contribute to the shared goals of Horizon Europe initiatives.

For the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities to be effective, U2Demo will prioritize tailored and customized messaging for each specific target audience.

2.1 Identification of Target Audiences

To ensure that the U2Demo project achieves its key objectives, the project has identified key messages according to specific target audiences to ensure that the developed solutions and tools are exploited to their full potential.

The U2Demo vision, goals and results will be disseminated across several target groups (Figure 2). Since the project is in its initial phase, this list might undergo some changes to adapt to the U2Demo strategies and solutions that will be developed.

Figure 2 - U2Demo Target Groups

One of the main target groups of the **U2Demo project** comprises Citizens, Media, and End Users, to disseminate information about the project. Initially, the focus will be on communicating the project’s goals and strategies, while in later stages, the emphasis will shift to sharing its results and achievements. This approach involves engaging the non-scientific public and end-users in discussions, encouraging the community to explore topics related to the project, such as the benefits of P2P energy trading, the developed solutions, their environmental impact, and their overall contributions to sustainable energy practices.

The D&C plan will also target more specific audiences that are further detailed in the next section, focusing on the stakeholders that may use or benefit directly from the research results in their own activities and work – such as the scientific community, policy makers or industry partners.

2.2 Key Messages and Channels by Target Audience

The tables below (Table 1, Table 2, Table 3, Table 4) show key messages and channels according to the four main target groups identified for the U2Demo project. As mentioned before, due to the multidisciplinary nature of the consortium, specific partners will reach specific target groups easier than others, according to their expertise and network. Thus, the consortium will be committed to assure effective communication to all identified audiences.

Table 1 - Target audience: Citizens, Media, and end Users - Goals and channels

Audiences	Goal	Activities	Communication Tools
Citizens	Raise awareness about the project strategies, goals and solutions.	Workshops, events	Website, social media, publications in media, press releases, newsletters, videos, rollups, flyers
Media	Enhance public opinion via media channels, to support the discussion on P2P energy sharing.	Outreach Events	Press releases and other media activities (opinion articles, interviews)
End Users <i>Energy consumers, prosumers, customers, Energy Cooperatives, System operators associations (e.g., E.DSO); Consumer organisations (e.g., ECC-Network); Energy generators' associations; IoT associations (e.g., AIOTI); Data Spaces (e.g., Gaia-X); Environmental organisations; Other non-profit;</i>	Inform about U2Demo solutions, tools, methodologies highlighting the advantages of P2P sharing technology.	Workshops, events	Website, social media, newsletters, videos, rollups

Table 2 - Target audience: Policy Makers and Regular Entities - Goals and channels

Audiences	Goal	Activities	Communication Tools
Policy Makers <i>At European, National, and Regional levels, including governments, governmental agencies, parliaments, EU commission, European Institutions</i>	<p>U2Demo will propose regulatory frameworks and policy recommendations for enabling P2P trading and energy sharing.</p> <p>Highlight the role that P2P energy sharing can play in achieving EU clean/sustainable energy goals. U2Demo's impactful results will guide the creation of new policies and attract funding for future community-driven energy initiatives.</p>	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, videos, newsletters, social media, flyers, publications in media, rollups, posters
Regular Entities <i>Standardization bodies such as IEC, IEEE, ISO, UNE, CEN, GBC; eBIX, BRIDGE</i>	<p>U2Demo will foster business ecosystems, support innovative energy sharing models, and influence policy priorities to attract more public funding opportunities.</p>	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, publications in media, newsletters, videos, rollups

Table 3 - Target audience: Industry and Scientific Communities - Goals and channels

Audiences	Goal	Activities
Energy-related Industry <i>Energy producers, system operators, Energy Communities, retailers and aggregators</i>	<p>U2Demo will deliver innovative tools, solutions, and business models for the widespread adoption of P2P energy trading and energy sharing.</p>	Workshops, events, scientific publications, conferences
Universities and R&I Centres <i>Scientific community, R&D, universities</i>	<p>U2Demo will share results from demonstration activities and provide cutting-edge insights from lessons learned.</p>	Workshops, events, scientific publications, conferences

European Research Projects <i>EU initiatives, programme projects/joint actions, European Open Science Cloud</i>	U2Demo will foster synergies with other European projects through collaborations such as BRIDGE Working Groups and peer project clusters.	Workshops, events, scientific publications, conferences
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Table 4 - Target audience: Services and Technology Providers – Goals and channels

Audiences	Goal	Activities	Communication Tools
Services Sector <i>Service companies, efficiency consultants</i>	U2Demo will deliver innovative solutions and business models to enable widespread adoption of P2P trading and energy sharing.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, newsletter, videos, rollups, flyers
Technology Providers <i>Companies developing software, platform provider with connectivity with the community platform, hardware devices, communication networks, building operators, weather services, data analytic tools, cybersecurity solutions, IoT devices</i>	U2Demo will develop and test scalable P2P trading and energy-sharing solutions across multiple demonstration sites.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, publications in media, newsletter, videos, rollups, flyers

3 Communication Channels and Tools

The communication channels and tools proposed in the current D&C Plan aim to increase the project's visibility, recognition, and awareness and to promote active engagement with the target audiences.

In the next sub-sections will be presented an overview of all the communication tools and channels: U2Demo Visual identity and Tools (Section 3.1), Website (Section 3.2), social media (Section 3.3), Newsletters (Section 3.4), Promotional Materials (Section 3.5), Media Activities (Section 3.6) and Videos (Section 3.7).

3.1 U2Demo Visual Identity and Tools

Together with a professional design agency, a project visual identity was developed and will be consistently applied in all the U2Demo channels, promotional materials, and tools, including:

- Website and social media channels;
- Branded stationery (email signature, web call background, etc.);
- Project official templates (Word; PowerPoint, LaTeX);
- Communication toolkit (flyers, project presentation, Roll Ups, posters);
- Videos.

This section presents the logo (Section 3.1.1), colour palette (Section 3.1.2), pilot icons (Section 3.1.3) and U2Demo templates (Section 3.1.4). The materials here presented are available to all U2Demo partners via U2Demo internal SharePoint and also available for download from the [U2Demo website](#).

3.1.1 U2Demo Logo and Rationale

The logotype is the main visual support of the project and must be present in all communication tools, channels, and materials. A preliminary version of the U2Demo was developed by the INESC ID team and submitted in the Grant Agreement. This initial version was then renewed and improved by a professional design team in the first month of the project. The final version of the logo was approved in the first Scientific Committee meeting. The rationale of the logo is presented in Figure 3. The final vertical and horizontal colour versions are presented in Figure 4 and the logos adapted to different backgrounds in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

The primary colours of the project are related to technology: **purple** (often used to convey a blend of creativity, innovation, mystery, transformation) and **blue** (Trust, reliability, security, professionalism, Europe, planet, fresh).

All elements combined represent the concept and vision of the project. The center of the logo consists of a white **key figure**, referring to **Citizens and Open Source**, surrounded by a circle divided into three parts. The left part of the circle is in blue, referring to **Social Equity**; the upper white part refers to **Power Supply** and the right part of the circle is in purple, referring to **Blockchain** (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Logo Rationale

The **U2Demo logo** is designed for use across multiple platforms, including websites, apps, and social media, and adapts to various backgrounds.

- On blue or purple backgrounds, the logo should be in a single color (white, Figure 5).
- On white or black backgrounds, the logo should feature a gradient (Figure 4).
- A one-color black version can also be used on a light grey background (see Figure 6).

Regarding **size requirements**:

- The minimum size is 3 cm for the vertical version and 1 cm for the horizontal version.
- Below these dimensions, only the icon (without text) should be used.

For further details, refer to the **Brand Guidelines** document in ANNEX I.

Figure 4 - Logo in colour, to be used on a white background

Figure 5 - Logo in colour, to be used on a dark background

Figure 6 - Logo in black and white

The **Citizen Icon** is also available as a standalone image, to be used in different kinds of communications. It is available in purple, for lighter backgrounds, and white, for darker backgrounds (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Citizen Icon (purple and white)

3.1.2 Colour Palette

U2Demo main colours, derivations and secondary colours are shown in Figure 8. The colour codes for web and print use are mentioned in the Brand Guidelines Document (ANNEX I). Key colors include **blue and purple**, symbolizing aspects like Europe, planet, creativity, transformation, and mystery.

Figure 8 - Colour Palette U2Demo

3.1.3 Pilot icons

The U2Demo project will be tested in four countries: Belgium, the Netherlands, Italy and Portugal. To represent each one of the Pilots, four image icons were developed by the design team. These icons consist of the **Citizen Icons placed on the country map**, and will be used to illustrate and support all visual tools and materials related to the Pilots (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Pilot Icons

3.1.4 U2Demo Templates

Within the project, several templates have been developed with the U2Demo visual identity described above to ensure a coherent and professional visual identity in the materials used by all consortia partners. All templates are available in a dedicated folder in U2Demo's internal SharePoint.

The available templates so far include **Word-format** templates (Deliverables, Internal reports, Meeting agenda, Meeting minutes, Meeting list of Attendance, News submission template and soon will be added also the Newsletter template), a [deliverable LaTeX template](#) and a **PowerPoint** template that has been developed by the design agency to be used by all partners for internal and external presentations (e.g., conferences, consortium meetings, public outreach, presented in ANNEX II).

If partners develop a non-existing template for their needs, they should also upload it to the U2Demo internal SharePoint folder so that it can also be used by other partners, if needed.

All templates shall contain the U2Demo logo, graphic elements of the project (See Brand Guidelines in ANNEX I) and the European Commission flag with the following disclaimer, acknowledging the EU funding, as mentioned in the grant agreement disclaimer below (Figure 10).

“Funded by European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101160684. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Figure 10 - EU Grant agreement disclaimer

3.2 U2Demo Website

The project website will be the main media hub for dissemination of U2Demo initiatives and serve as a repository of all the project activities during the project lifecycle and beyond. The U2Demo public website domain is: <https://u2demo.eu/> and was launched at the beginning of M2 (October of 2024). Language: English.

The website structure was planned to allow easy access to information and navigation, organizing the existing content in a coherent and intuitive way. Attention was paid to implementing a clear and consistent design and navigation system that helps users easily find

what they're looking for: a menu bar with easily recognizable labels and submenus for more detailed categories.

The website will target all audiences identified earlier (Section 2) and aims to promote interactions with other initiatives, projects, and working groups to increase public awareness and engagement.

Website structure:

The website features a simple, modern and accessible design using the U2Demo brand identity. The website has a responsive design to ensure that it is accessible and usable across different devices and screen sizes (smartphones, tablets, laptops).

The overall goal is to create a website that is easy to navigate with clear contents and cross-platform support. A brief description of the website content and structure follows.

Homepage:

The Homepage header (Figure 11) consists of an animated image that reflects the project main vision and the concept behind the Logotype.

Figure 11 - Website Header and main Menu

The **Homepage** includes the U2Demo logo, a section “in brief” or “in numbers” with facts about the project (duration of the project, number of partners and countries involved, number of demonstration sites and use cases, and funding), a text box with the U2Demo vision, a section with the latest news and next events, logos and names of the consortium partners, and a footer

with links to U2Demo social media (BlueSky and LinkedIn), link for CORDIS, ZENODO and GITHUB website, and the European Commission logo and disclaimer.

The website **Menu** is divided into four main Tabs, to allow a more intuitive and easy navigation through all the contents. Next is a brief description of each sub-menu: About, Research & Innovation, Media & Events and Contact.

About:

The About section is split in three sub-sections:

- **Overview and Mission:** with essential information about the project, its mission, goals, and objectives.
- **Consortium:** with information about the Consortium partners. This page includes a European map with partners distributed according to their Home Country, and identified by an icon that represents their area of activity (Research Center/University, Utility, Technology Provider, Foundation/Association, Municipality, Services Provider and Industry). Under the Map are listed the partner Logos with a click button that leads to an individual page for each partner that will include: a Description of the Institution, Role within the Project and link to their website and social media Channels.
- **Work Packages (WP):** with information about each WP. By clicking on each WP tab, one can see the description and the Lead partner.

Research & Innovation:

The U2Demo R&I Section provides an overview of the Research activities planned for each Pilot and to keep a record of the main resources of the project: scientific publications and public deliverables.

This section is divided into three sub-sections for an easy access to information:

- **Pilots:** pilot pages provide more detailed information about the Demo sites. By clicking on each icon, one can see the objectives, use cases that will be tested in each demo and images of the sites.
- **Deliverables:** will provide access to all public project Deliverables.
- **Publications:** will list all project Publications (Journal Papers, Conference Papers, Posters and Presentations at Conferences).
- **Thesis:** will list all project PhD/MSc theses on the subject.

Media & Events:

The Media & Events section includes all the announcements of activities related to the communication and dissemination of the project including news, information about events, Newsletters, and brand materials for Download.

This section is divided in four sub-sections:

- **News:** to disclose all the information about U2Demo latest activities and initiatives, the communication team will regularly produce and share news articles for the website.
- **Events:** to announce all future events related to the Project
- **Newsletters:** to provide access and allow the download of the Project Newsletters, plus display a newsletter subscription form.
- **Logo & Promotional Materials:** to share the project Logos and promotional materials for consultation and/or download (Logotype, Brand Guidelines, flyers, etc.)

Contact:

The Contact Us page (Figure 12) provides a form requiring name, email, subject and message. The form is linked to the u2demo.dissemination@inesc-id.pt mailing list and the U2Demo coordination team at INESC ID will receive and reply to all messages. The data collected will be stored during the project and deleted at the end of it. This page also provides information about the Coordination Institution contacts and how to connect on social media.

GET IN TOUCH
CONTACT US

CONTACT DETAILS

INESC ID – INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM LISBOA

Rua Alves Redol 9
1000 029 Lisboa
Portugal

CONNECT WITH US**LET'S GET IN TOUCH**

Name

E-mail

Subject

Your message (opcional)

Figure 12 - Contact Page

3.2.1 Technical Development and Management

The U2Demo website was developed by a design agency using WordPress, an open-source content management software and GoDaddy, that provides services related to domain registration, website hosting, website building, and online marketing.

REScoop.Vlaanderen, the task leader, will be responsible for the management of the website and content update, with the contribution of all partners. The website will be maintained for at least 5 years, which means that it will remain alive for 2 years after the end of the project.

3.2.2 Search-Engine Optimization (SEO) and Analytics

The website will be Search-Engine optimization-friendly to improve its visibility to search engines such as Google, and Yahoo, among others. REScoop.Vlaanderen will be responsible for analyzing the website traffic through google analytics, collecting data on the number of visitors, average duration of visits, number of page views, and number of references to the project on search engines.

This data will be used to monitor the visibility of the website and, when necessary, to plan strategies to increase its popularity. This information will be collected for the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) checks throughout the project.

3.3 U2Demo Social Media

In addition to the project's website, **U2Demo** will place a strong emphasis on online activities, particularly through its social media channel (LinkedIn).

Web-based platforms are increasingly valuable for connecting individuals and organizations, offering opportunities to **engage with broader audiences, establish meaningful dialogue, and build relationships**. U2Demo's primary objective is to expand and actively engage its audience on these platforms through consistent online interaction. The project's social media presence will be amplified by leveraging the extensive networks of its partners to build a robust and impactful U2Demo social media identity. To drive engagement from specific stakeholders and highlight key topics, strategic use of **hashtags** (e.g., #U2Demo, #EnergySharing, #P2PEnergy, #SustainableEnergy) and relevant **handles** (e.g., @HorizonEU, @EnergyCommunities, @Cinea, @U2Demo) will be employed.

U2Demo's social media channels will serve as a dynamic hub for sharing the latest project updates, including **publications, newsletters, event** announcements, and news from the **demonstration sites**. These platforms will also **spotlight U2Demo partners** and their achievements, inform followers about **project activities**, and engage with **related initiatives** and projects.

Social media efforts aim to increase interest in U2Demo, foster participation in its events and activities, encourage audiences to follow the project outputs, and ultimately **inspire the adoption of U2Demo's solutions and strategies**.

All U2Demo partners are expected to contribute content and actively support these channels by sharing, liking, and commenting on posts. By combining partner efforts and an active presence, U2Demo's social media strategy is designed to maximize outreach, build engagement, and drive the project's impact.

All U2Demo social media accounts will be maintained in English to ensure accessibility to a wide audience. These accounts are public and will be managed throughout the project by REScoop.Vlaanderen, the leader of the Dissemination and Communication work package.

To increase visibility, interactions, and followers, the following common strategies will be implemented across U2Demo's social media platforms:

- A minimum of one publication per week.
- **Monthly assessments** of social media analytics to monitor public engagement and adjust strategies as needed to improve visibility. These analytics will also feed into KPI evaluations.
- All posts will consistently follow the **visual identity** developed for U2Demo.
- Posts will tag relevant partners and stakeholders using @ mentions, encouraging them to share U2Demo content on their institutional channels.
- Most posts will include **videos and images** to boost audience engagement.
- All social media channels will be prominently featured on the U2Demo website and highlighted in dissemination materials and project presentations.

To ensure continuous engagement and a steady flow of content, U2Demo will also implement targeted **Social Media Campaigns** as part of its strategy. By maintaining a regular posting schedule, aligning content with the project's visual identity, and utilizing analytics-driven adjustments, U2Demo aims to maximize its impact and audience reach through its social media platforms.

3.3.1 U2Demo Social Media Campaigns:

To present and introduce the U2Demo large consortium, the plan is to prepare a regular **partner post** with information about each partner and a quote with their role under the project, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - U2Demo Partner post for INESC-ID

Once the demonstration activities start, and with the help of the partners involved, the plan is to regularly upload photos and developments on social media. Additionally, specific campaigns will mark Celebration Days as for example the EU Energy Day or World Energy Day.

3.3.2 U2Demo LinkedIn

The **U2Demo LinkedIn account** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/u2demo/>) has been active since **M1 (September 2024)**. A customized banner was designed for the LinkedIn header, incorporating U2Demo's graphic elements, logo, and tagline. The LinkedIn homepage provides an overview of the project, including its objectives and activities, along with a direct link to the U2Demo project website. This platform allows for more detailed posts than X/Twitter, making it ideal for sharing comprehensive updates on U2Demo's outputs, events, and activities (Figure 14).

As of **February 26th, 2025**, almost six months after the launch of the U2Demo LinkedIn account, the channel had **187 followers**. These promising numbers highlight the potential for further growth. By the end of the project, the aim is to have built a significantly larger network of professionals spanning the energy value chain.

To achieve this, the Coordination team will ensure that the LinkedIn account is regularly updated with relevant and engaging content tailored to the needs of U2Demo's stakeholders. REScoop.Vlaanderen, as the work package leader, will rely on the U2Demo consortium members to actively participate by following the account, sharing posts, and engaging through comments. This collective effort will enable U2Demo to reach a wide and diverse community

of stakeholders and potential users, ensuring effective knowledge transfer and dissemination of the project's results.

The image shows a screenshot of the U2Demo LinkedIn profile page. At the top, there is a banner with the text "Empowering Citizens through Energy Sharing" and an icon of a laptop with people icons. Below the banner is the U2Demo profile picture and name. The bio states: "Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy democratization. Funded by Horizon EU (GA no. 101160684)". It also mentions "Research Services · 187 followers · 11-50 employees". There are buttons for "Message", "Following", and a menu icon. Below the navigation tabs (Home, About, Posts, Jobs, People), the "Overview" section contains a paragraph: "The U2Demo Horizon Europe project coordinated by the Portuguese R&D Institute INESC-ID, aims to create innovative, consumer-centered management strategies that facilitate a widespread participation in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trading and Energy Sharing. This initiative will promote equitable and ... see more". A "Show all details" link is present. The "Page posts" section shows two posts. The first post is from U2Demo, dated 42m, with the text: "On Friday, U2Demo will be presented at the BRIDGE Knowledge Sharing Session on Cross-Sector and Multi-Energy Integration, ...more". It includes a graphic with the text "bridge #bridgeEU". The second post is a "Partner Spotlight" for TNO, dated 1d, with the text: "We're excited to highlight TNO, a key ...more". It includes a graphic with the TNO logo and a quote from Aliene van der Veen: "We develop solutions for smart grid integration and decentralized energy systems, with a strong focus on sustainability and responsibility. By connecting ICT, regulation and consumer needs, we create a valuable link between technology, policy, and everyday energy use."

Figure 14 - LinkedIn Profile Page

3.3.3 U2Demo X/Twitter and BlueSky

The U2Demo project initially launched with a **X/Twitter account, which is in the process of being replaced by a U2Demo BlueSky account**, introduced on January 21, 2025. This transition reflects a strategic move to engage with a more professional and contextually relevant online community, aligning with the values of European Horizon2020 projects and fostering a collaborative environment focused on innovation and sustainable energy.

U2Demo will aim to post regularly on this platform, with at least **one post per month**, depending on the availability of content. Suggested hashtags to increase engagement and visibility are mentioned above.

Project partners are encouraged to support the BlueSky account by **liking, reposting, and commenting** on U2Demo posts. This will help amplify the project's messages and foster engagement within the decentralized social media community. By transitioning entirely to BlueSky, U2Demo aims to build a broad and diverse audience, enhancing the dissemination of its key messages and promoting collaboration within the sustainable energy and open-source energy communities.

Suggested **hashtags** include: #U2Demo #HorizonEurope #SustainableEnergy #P2PEnergy #EnergySharing #OpenSourceEnergy #EnergyDemocracy #Collaboration #EnergyInnovation

The goal is to grow this audience significantly, with a target of at least **200 followers**. To achieve this, the account administrator will actively engage with relevant audiences by following, re-tweeting, commenting, and liking posts from related accounts.

The **U2Demo X/Twitter account** (@U2Demo, <https://x.com/U2Demo>) has been set up in **M1 (September 2024)**. The account's header has been tailored to reflect U2Demo's visual identity, including its graphic elements, logo, and tagline (Figure 15).

Due to the nature of the platform, U2Demo posts on X/Twitter are concise (maximum of 280 characters) and will utilize engaging visuals, such as video clips and animated images, to share updates on project developments, news articles, activities, and events. Posts incorporate relevant hashtags to increase visibility and audience engagement.

As of **Feb 26th, 2025**, the U2Demo X/Twitter account had **38 followers** and **21 posts**.

Figure 15 - X/Twitter Profile Page

The **U2Demo BlueSky** account (@U2Demo.bsky.social, <https://bsky.app/profile/u2demo.bsky.social>) was launched on **January 21, 2025**, replacing the project's presence on X/Twitter (Figure 16).

The account's header and profile were designed to align with **U2Demo's visual identity**, ensuring consistency across platforms. Posts on BlueSky will share project updates, news, events, and activities, using concise text and engaging visuals. As of **February 25, 2025**, the BlueSky account had 1 follower and 1 post.

Figure 16 - U2Demo BlueSky Profile Page

3.4 U2Demo Newsletters

The **U2Demo Consortium** will release a quarterly digital newsletter to highlight its initiatives, including updates on news, events, and published materials. This newsletter will be distributed via email, shared on U2Demo's social media channels, and made available on the project website. Subscription (and an easy unsubscribe option) to the newsletter will be accessible through the U2Demo website.

The newsletters will be in digital format and distributed through a **mailing platform: Brevo**. They will provide concise yet informative updates on the project, consortium activities, and results, with direct links to the U2Demo website for further details.

Each edition will feature the following sections:

- A brief **editorial** written by the project coordinator or work package leaders, discussing the project's status or relevant topics in energy sharing and P2P trading developments.
- A section on **events**, covering past and upcoming activities.
- Updates on **project activities**, including major milestones and demonstrations.
- A spotlight on the **consortium**, which may include partner highlights, interviews, or special achievements.
- A section dedicated to **publications** produced within the project.
- Information about **upcoming events** relevant to U2Demo's themes.

The newsletter will also provide links to the U2Demo website and social media platforms, along with information on how to subscribe to future issues. All consortium partners are encouraged to contribute content for inclusion.

The first newsletter issue is scheduled for **March 2025**. Prior to its release, it will circulate among the Scientific Committee for approval via the project mailing list. Once finalized, it will be distributed electronically to subscribers, promoted on social media, and made available on the newsletter section of the U2Demo website. This collaborative and structured approach ensures comprehensive dissemination of U2Demo's progress and achievements.

3.5 U2Demo Promotional Materials

To support the promotion of the **U2Demo project** at events and other onsite initiatives, a comprehensive communication toolkit will be developed and updated as needed.

All U2Demo promotional materials will feature the project logo, and where appropriate, the tagline "Empowering Communities through Energy Sharing." These materials will adhere to U2Demo's visual identity, including the designated colours and graphic elements, as outlined in Section 3.1 and ANNEX I. Additionally, all materials will prominently display the European flag and include the required EU funding disclaimer.

Some U2Demo materials have already been developed and are available in the internal SharePoint folder, including a **U2Demo Flyer** (print version and digital version, Figure 17) and a **Roll-Up Banner** (Figure 18).

- The flyer is an A5 bi-fold brochure with 4 pages, providing an overview of the project's vision, goals, demonstration sites, and consortium.
- The roll-up banner measures 85x200cm and is intended for use at exhibitions, events, and conferences.

These materials are **available on the U2DEMO Website for download** (LINK) and are available in both PDF and editable formats (Adobe Illustrator) in the project **internal SharePoint**. This editable version allows partners to customize, translate, and adapt the materials to meet their specific needs for meetings, conferences, and other events.

Additional materials will be developed throughout the project, tailored to the needs of the consortium and specific campaigns. These materials will play a crucial role in disseminating and exploiting project results. **Partners may create materials independently**, provided they follow the established **branding guidelines**. All created materials should be shared with the consortium and uploaded to the U2Demo internal SharePoint to ensure consistency and accessibility for all partners.

The U2Demo project (Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy democratization) aims to create innovative, consumer-centered management strategies that facilitate a widespread participation in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trading and energy sharing. Launched in September 2024, the project will promote equitable and democratic access to sustainable energy resources.

Funded by European Union's Horizon Innovation Action programme, under grant agreement no. 101160684, U2Demo brings together nineteen participant partners, including 2 associated partners, from eight countries, pooling their expertise to develop strategies that will be seamlessly integrated into open-source, non-proprietary tools and platforms. These solutions align with principles of openness, technology neutrality, interoperability, scalability, replicability, reliability, security, and trustworthiness.

These strategies will undergo testing in 4 pilots within at least four diverse Energy Communities, located in Italy, Belgium, Netherlands and Portugal and each with unique attributes and governance models.

The overarching objective is to assess advanced P2P trading and Energy-sharing tools, determine optimal implementation conditions, and consolidate the most promising solutions and associated business models.

U2Demo in Numbers

42 months	17 partners + 2 associated	September 2024 to February 2028
8 Countries	4 Pilots	5 M€ EU Funding

The Four pilots

Belgium Pilot

Flanders, Antwerp

In Belgium, the pilot will have a strong social feature, focusing on overcoming energy poverty, as the demo will take place in a social housing neighborhood in the province of Antwerp. This pilot will be led by Klimaan, a local cooperative managing a Citizen Energy Community (CEC) in the Oltrefeek social neighborhood. The area faces low acceptance of new concepts by residents, resulting in an excess of solar energy due to low demand. One of the project's objectives is to analyze the reasons for this situation and explore ways to overcome it.

Dutch Pilot

Hague, Netherlands

Living Lab Scheweningen is the flagship programme of The Hague's Smart City activities where the municipality, companies, residents and research institutions look for smart and digital inventions to solve societal challenges. Since last year, a collaboration with the local GSO (STEVIN) started allowing the development of deeper studies involving grid factors and the test of flexibility services.

Portuguese Pilot

Evora, Portugal

The Portuguese pilot will be located in Valverde, a small rural village in Evora with about 400 inhabitants. Valverde was already involved in projects like DOWNS and InterGrid, and is equipped with advanced devices for local energy monitoring and control. In this pilot, the project will test the concept of Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading within a Renewable Energy Community (REC) to evaluate and compare energy-sharing algorithms in a regulated environment.

Italian Pilot

Teramo, Italy

The Demo is based in an operative Renewable Energy Community (REC) in Vallepiave managed by Endream. The REC involves 10 buildings: 5 of these can be considered prosumers (as they produce, self-consume and share their renewable energy production) and the remaining 5 are consumers (which can use the low-cost energy produced by the other members of the REC). The goal of this Demo is to phase out natural gas, before 2024 by replacing gas boilers with heat pumps, conventional stoves with induction ones and supporting peak loads with solar water heaters.

Coordinator

Beneficiary Partners

Associated Partners

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Innovation Actions under grant agreement no. 101160684. Views and opinions expressed in this document are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (ECIEA), neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

u2demo.eu

Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy Democratization

Empowering Citizens through Energy Sharing

Figure 17 - U2Demo Flyer (bi-fold document)

Figure 18 - U2Demo Roll-Up Banner

3.6 U2Demo Media Activities

To share the **U2Demo Project** initiatives with a broader audience, the Communication team at **REScoop.Vlaanderen** will focus on enhancing the visibility of the project's achievements and activities through targeted media outreach.

Press Releases (PR) will serve as a primary tool for disseminating U2Demo's progress and outcomes to the media at local, national, and European levels. The objective is to generate media coverage that highlights the project's key results and impacts. To date, **1 press release** has been issued in both Portuguese and English, announcing the launch of the project. To this date, two articles in general media have been published about the U2Demo project.

Future press releases will focus on major milestones, such as the start of demonstration activities and their outcomes. Toward the end of the project, a comprehensive press release summarizing U2Demo's achievements will be prepared and distributed to both national and international media by INESC ID. Consortium members will also be encouraged to disseminate this final PR in their respective countries, ensuring the project reaches a global audience.

Additional media activities may be planned throughout the project to further increase visibility. These could include negotiating feature articles with journalists, arranging interviews, or

publishing opinion pieces closer to the project's conclusion, when significant results are available.

All partners are encouraged to contribute to media outreach by developing their own press releases and engaging in media activities to promote U2Demo in their local contexts. When such publications are planned, partners must notify the Coordination Team via the dedicated mailing list (u2demo.coordination@inesc-id.pt). The Coordination Team will maintain a database of all published materials and ensure they are shared on the U2Demo website's news section and social media platforms under the tag **"In the Media."**

This coordinated approach will maximize U2Demo's exposure, ensuring its achievements are recognized across all consortium countries and beyond.

3.7 U2Demo Videos

During the preparation of the proposal, one video was proposed featuring the activities developed at the demonstration sites. Since demo activities will only start at M13, in October 2025, the video will be developed later on, with the support of a professional video production company.

4 Dissemination Activities

In **Section 3**, the communication tools and channels were introduced to disseminate **U2Demo** initiatives and results to a wide audience. **Section 4** focuses on the dissemination activities planned to raise awareness of the project's outcomes and, more importantly, make them publicly accessible so that stakeholders can utilize them in various domains, such as research, policymaking, training, and other initiatives.

Dissemination activities will play a vital role in promoting P2P energy-sharing research to aspiring researchers while engaging other relevant communities. These efforts include the publication of scientific research articles and books (**Section 4.1**), participation in conferences and workshops (**Section 4.2**), the organization of workshops and events (**Section 4.3**), and the development of patents and establishment of synergies with peer projects (**Section 4.4**).

These planned actions will ensure that participant partners from research, industry, and academia, in compliance with contractual obligations, disseminate and effectively exploit the results generated within U2Demo. Lastly, **Section 4.5** provides an overview of the consortium's participation rules regarding dissemination activities. This approach will ensure a structured, collaborative effort to maximize the impact of U2Demo's findings.

4.1 U2Demo Scientific Research Publications

The main objective of the U2Demo project is to develop open-source tools and platforms that promote fair and inclusive access to green energy resources within active consumers and ECs. Thus, in line with the priorities of the European Commission, the U2Demo consortium will adopt an **Open Science strategy**, including open access, open data, collaborative participation, transparency, reproducibility, accessibility, security and reliability of the research outputs.

This Open Science strategy includes publishing scientific articles in **peer-reviewed Open Access scientific journals** (and also journals that support Open Access), such as *Renewable Energy Journal*, *Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy*, *IEEE Transaction on Green Communications and Networking*, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids*, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, *Sustainable Cities and Society*, *Distributed Ledger Technologies: Research and Practice*, *Electric Power Systems Research* journals and *Open Research Europe*, for the findings to be available to all researchers and public in general.

The U2Demo project will provide immediate **open access to published scientific articles and results** through trusted European Commission repositories (e.g., Zenodo, Open Research Europe platform, EIRIE platform, Energy Community repository) and license them under CC BY (or equivalent) or CC BY-NC/ND (or equivalent). U2Demo will preferentially opt for the **open peer-review process** and for sharing the scientific publications even before the

peer-review process, through pre-prints (e.g arXiv.org), following an “early and open sharing” approach.

The Coordination Team at INESC ID has developed a List (available in Sharepoint), outlining all the Work packages and tasks that have the potential to submit publications. A list of Conferences where these publications could be submitted was also listed and shared with the consortium.

All partners should inform the U2Demo Coordination Team (U2Demo.coordination@inesc-id.pt) about the submitted and accepted publications (Section 4.5). By the end of the project is expected to have at least 21 scientific articles published among all consortium partners.

4.2 U2Demo Participation in Events/Conferences

To achieve its communication and dissemination objectives, the **U2Demo project** will identify key national and international events to ensure participation across a wide range of initiatives. Consortium partners are encouraged to engage in local and national events, such as Open Days hosted by universities and research institutions, or broader events like the European Researchers’ Night, to raise awareness of the project among diverse audiences.

U2Demo will also focus on sharing innovative solutions, tools, and technological advancements at specialized conferences, such as the **Sustainable Cities and Society, Distributed Ledger Technologies: Research and Practice, Electric Power Systems Research, IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids, IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Open Research Europe**, as well as other scientific forums. These efforts, led primarily by academic partners, will be complemented by collaborations with peer projects, including those under the **BRIDGE initiative**.

Additionally, U2Demo will maintain a strong presence at key industry events, such as **ENLIT**. This annual forum attracts high-profile speakers and participants from business communities, universities, research centers, EU policymakers, media, and energy stakeholders. Regular presentations to Participation in events will vary based on partner expertise. For example, industry partners will prioritize workshops and client meetings, while research partners will focus on scientific conferences and forums. To ensure coordination, partners are required to notify the Coordination Team at u2demo.coordination@inesc-id.pt at least two weeks in advance.

By **M6**, U2Demo had already participated in several events reaching different target audiences:

- **22-24 October 2024:** Participation in [ENLIT 2024](#) in Milan, Italy, where INESC ID promoted U2Demo at its booth. Enlit is one of the most significant events in the

energy sector, bringing together industry leaders, innovators, and policymakers from around the world.

- **18-20 November 2024:** Showcase of U2Demo supported research by Diana Estefanía Chérrez Barragán at the [IEEE URUCON 2024](#) conference.

The following events are also scheduled for 2025:

- **6-7 March 2025:** General Assembly Meeting of the U2Demo consortium in Paris
- **Under assessment:**
 - **10-12 June 2025:** European Sustainable Energy Week in Brussels
 - **23 September 2025:** AIOTI Days 2025 in Madrid
 - **4-6 November 2025:** Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC) in Barcelona
 - **18-20 November 2025:** ENLIT Europe in Bilbao
 - **And:** Smart Cities Summit; Participation in European Grid Forum workshops (GRIFOn); ... (TBD)

These activities are instrumental in disseminating and exploiting project results, ensuring that U2Demo's innovations are effectively communicated and transferred to target stakeholders. To measure the impact of these efforts, the project consortium employs a set of metrics and KPIs to monitor progress and achievements (see Table 5). This structured approach ensures that dissemination activities are aligned with U2Demo's objectives and deliver meaningful outcomes.

4.3 Organization of Workshops/Events

U2Demo partners will organize at least four workshops, one for each demonstration site. The primary aim of these workshops is to inform stakeholders about **U2Demo's solutions, tools, and methodologies** while fostering collaboration with other relevant initiatives outlined in Section 5.

The demonstration site workshops will target all identified audience groups, ensuring broad participation. Since the demonstration activities are set to begin at **M13**, these workshops are planned to take place during the second and third years of the project.

These events are expected to enhance collaboration with other initiatives, projects, and programs, providing a platform for the exchange of research findings, insights, and dissemination activities, while strengthening U2Demo's network and impact.

4.4 Synergies with Peer Projects

U2Demo partners are committed to fostering liaisons and joint activities with other European research projects, communities, and initiatives. These synergies will primarily target **scientific communities** and the **energy-related industry**, including system operators and aggregators.

U2Demo has joined the **BRIDGE initiative**. BRIDGE is structured into four specific working groups (WGs): **regulation, business models, data management, and customer engagement**. U2Demo has assigned expert partners to participate in each WG, such as those pertaining to Data Management, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement, and Business Models, ensuring that the project contributes to and benefits from this collaborative framework.

Additionally, U2Demo is set to take part in occasions that foster connections and synergies/liaisons with fellow European projects, exemplified by its participation in events like ENLIT Networking events, EU Sustainable Energy Week. These activities aim to strengthen U2Demo's connections with other initiatives, facilitating knowledge exchange and enhancing the impact of the project. E.g. U2Demo is already part of [List of Projects and Initiatives | int:net Community](#)

U2Demo will also seek opportunities to engage with the Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI), participate in clusters of digital projects to foster the development of the digital and ICT technologies to address current energy challenges, and to participate in energy communities' initiatives/action.

4.5 Guidelines on Consortium Participation in Dissemination Activities

To maintain a comprehensive and up-to-date record of all **U2Demo** activities, partners are required to adhere to the following guidelines:

Participation in **Events, Scientific Meetings, Congresses, and Workshops**:

- A minimum of **two weeks before** the activity, the partners should send an e-mail to the Coordination u2demo.coordination@inesc-id.pt. This prior notice is required for the Project Coordination Team to advertise the activity on time on social media and the website. The mail should include the following details about the activity:
 - type of activity
 - date
 - title
 - audience
 - the role of the partner

- Additionally, participants are also encouraged to share the activity among the **consortium** (u2demo.consortium@inesc-id.pt) and stakeholders, to increase network opportunities with project partners and stakeholders.
- During or right after the activity, the partner should
 - o Create a folder in the U2Demo internal SharePoint under “**WP 7 – Events**” (alternatively they can send the information to the coordination mailing list),
 - o Fill in the template “News and Events Submission form” ([LINK](#)) with relevant information about their participation, and
 - o Upload photos of their participation, abstract, article or poster presented and/or presentation.

Publication of **Scientific Article, PhD/Theses or other Publications:**

- All partners should **inform the U2Demo Coordination Team** (u2demo.coordination@inesc-id.pt) about all submitted and accepted publications – this information is collected for the U2Demo publication database (management record) and will be shared on the project website and social media.
- All publications, including scientific articles, should include the following **disclaimer** (under the acknowledgement section): *“Funded by European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101160684. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”*

5 Evaluation and Monitoring of D&C Activities

To evaluate the impact of the project’s dissemination activities, the U2Demo consortium has established, during proposal preparation, a specific set of metrics to monitor its achievements effectively. The KPIs have been revised and are presented in Table 5 and Table 6. The KPIs will be monitored throughout the whole project, monthly, to help evaluate project progress and to develop interim and annual reports.

Table 5 - Communication tools and channels, and KPIs

Channel	KPI	Targets	M6 Status	Expected Impact
U2Demo Website	No. of unique visitors	2,000	238 (starting from Jan 19th, 2025)	Main online information channel; Communication of project news, events & outcomes; liaisons with other initiatives, projects, WG; increase awareness and engagement with the project.
	Average duration of visits	2 min	1m07s	
	No. of page views	5,000	854	
U2Demo X/Twitter and BlueSky	No. of accumulative followers X/Twitter	200	38	Increased visibility and interest of TGs (Figure 2.1) and citizens; direct communication with followers, engagement with the project.
	No. of accumulative followers BlueSky	/	1	
	No. of tweets on X/Twitter	300	21	
	No. of tweets on BlueSky	/	1	
U2Demo LinkedIn	No. of accumulative followers	500	187	Increased visibility and interest of TGs (Figure 2.1) and citizens; direct communication with followers, engagement with the project.
Publications in general media	No. of articles in magazines, newspapers	10	2	Increased project visibility and impact on society.
Dissemination kit	No. of press releases (PR=2); factsheets/brochures (F/B=2); presentations (Pr=1); posters (Po=2); banners (B=1); eNewsletters (eN=6); videos (v=1)		- PR: 1 - F/B: 1 - Pr: 1 - Po: 0 - B: 1 - eN: 0 - V: 1	Communication of project news, events & results; Increased awareness. Unique branding and visual identity of the project.

Table 6 - Impact of the U2Demo project's dissemination activities

KPI	Targets	M6 Status	Dissemination Activities Aims	Tools and Channels
No. of workshops organised	5	0	Dissemination of results towards Target Groups, identification of cooperation opportunities, increased awareness, encouragement of citizens and external ECs involvement.	Project presentation, poster, brochure, leaflets, invitation, project social channels, website, media news
No. of attendees to the project workshops	25	0		
No. of demo events	4	0		
No. of webinars	4	0		
No. of attended events	20	4	Dissemination and exchange during conferences and fairs attracting energy system stakeholders.	Brochure, leaflets, poster, roll-up
No. of events where the project has been presented	5	2	Validation of the project's concept, findings, and advantages; Promotion of results to scientific communities; Ideas gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant TGs and initiatives.	Project presentation, roll-up, poster
No. of scientific publications	20	1	Validation of the project's concept, findings, and advantages; Promotion of results to scientific communities; Ideas gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant TGs and initiatives.	Conferences, scientific press media
No. of PhD/MSc thesis	6	0	Dissemination of academic insights and project findings within educational institutions.	Project website and social channels
No. of articles in magazines/journals	12	0	Promotion of U2Demo results and awareness among industry professionals and the broader public.	Industry press media, top conferences.
Liaisons and joint activities with other projects, communities, initiatives	12	0	Ideas gathering, knowledge and best practice exchange with similar initiatives. Joint events, publications.	Website links, workshops, joint publications, social media promotion
No. of scientific/technical dissemination material	3	0	Communication of U2Demo results and achievements.	Website, brochure, leaflets, poster

6 Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the initial plan for the communication and dissemination activities of the **U2Demo project**, designed to maximize its impact. A critical first step was to establish a strong visual identity, branding, and structured online presence to serve as the foundation for all dissemination and communication (D&C) efforts.

From **months 1 to 6**, the primary focus of **WP7** was on building a cohesive visual and brand identity to support a wide range of D&C activities. This included creating a recognizable **logo** and **brand image**, ensuring U2Demo initiatives are visually unified and impactful throughout the project lifecycle. Key milestones achieved during this period included the launch of the **U2Demo social media accounts**, which play a vital role in raising awareness, increasing visibility, and driving engagement. By month 6, the project's **LinkedIn** and **X/Twitter** accounts had already garnered traction, with LinkedIn reaching **187 followers**, while the X/Twitter account was discontinued in favor of **launching the BlueSky account** to better align with the project's goals. Moving forward, the coordination team will implement specific campaigns to further grow these numbers and deepen engagement with target audiences.

The development of the **U2Demo website** was another major achievement during this period, as it serves as the project's primary online communication hub. The website was carefully structured to ensure relevance and ease of access to project information, providing a central platform for updates, news, and stakeholder engagement.

To support dissemination efforts, templates for various communication needs were created, and several dissemination activities were initiated. For instance, a **scientific article** is under preparation, a **conference paper** was published on an international event, and U2Demo partners have attended **four events** to date, with three more currently under evaluation.

The deliverable also highlights the crucial role of consortium partners in supporting these efforts. The **U2Demo consortium**, comprising multidisciplinary entities with specialized expertise and established networks, is pivotal in reaching a diverse range of stakeholders. Their active participation in implementing the D&C strategy will significantly enhance the project's impact across **industry, academia, authorities, and society**.

Finally, this deliverable is considered a **living document** and will be updated at **M24**, or earlier, if necessary, to reflect changes or new developments.

ANNEX I: STANDARD STYLE GUIDELINES

Standard Style Guidelines

The U2Demo Brand Guidelines document ([LINK](#)) establishes a consistent visual identity, ensuring cohesive communication across various platforms.

The brand embodies key themes: Open Source, Social Equity, Power Supply, Blockchain, and Community. These principles shape the logo and overall visual identity.

It defines the logo **usage** (in vertical and horizontal formats), the **colour palette**, the visibility with proper margins and **placement**, and **dimensions**: the logo's minimum size is 3 cm; below this, only the icon is used.

The brand guidelines document establishes design rules: there should be no distortion, drop shadows, or alterations to spacing or gradients. The typography is Gilroy for branding materials and Arial for official documents (deliverables, internal, and mid-term reports), with the following text sizes:

- size 11 for body text
- 16 for titles
- 14 for subtitles
- and 12 for sub-subtitles.

The Brand Guidelines document also includes roll-ups, social banners, and other branded materials listed earlier in the document.

Beyond the Brand Guidelines, template documents are available on U2Demo SharePoint. See ANNEX II for examples.

Structure

This margin is designed to protect the logo to always be readable on the various formats.

Dimensions

This is the smallest dimension that the logo can be.

Typography

Our main font is Gilroy for text and titles.

Gilroy

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
- ! @ # \$ % & / \ | 0 []

	Italic	
Thin	ABC19	ABC19
Light	ABC19	ABC19
Regular	ABC19	ABC19
Medium	ABC19	ABC19
Semi Bold	ABC19	ABC19
Bold	ABC19	ABC19
Extra Bold	ABC19	ABC19
Block	ABC19	ABC19

Typography

For documents

Arial

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp
Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
- ! @ # \$ % & / \ | 0 []

Regular **A B C 1 9**
Bold **A B C 1 9**

ANNEX II: AVAILABLE TEMPLATES

These materials are available for all participants: a [PowerPoint template for presentations \(Annex II - Figure 19\)](#), an [Overview PowerPoint presentation](#) outlining the project's goals, consortium, and work package structure (**Annex II – Figure 20**), a [meeting minutes](#) template (**Annex II – Figure 21**), a [LaTeX template](#) accessible via Overleaf (**Annex II – Figure 22**), and a [News and Events template](#) (**Annex II – Figure 23**).

Figure 19 - Template Powerpoint

Project Overview U2DEMO

Innovative, consumer-centered management strategies that facilitate a widespread participation in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trading and Energy Sharing.

September 2024 – February 2028

Climate, Energy and Mobility project under Horizon Innovation Actions

Funded by the European Union

About

Mission
Approach
Consortium
Four Pilots
Four Phases
Work Packages

- 42 months
- September 2024 to February 2028
- 16 partners + 2 associated
- 8 Countries
- 4 PILOTS
- 5 M€ EU Funding

Mission

Creating innovative, consumer-centered management strategies to facilitate a widespread participation in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trading and energy sharing.

Goal: equitable and democratic access to sustainable energy resources.

Approach

- Evaluating P2P trading tools, identifying optimal models and business cases.
- Strategies will be tested in four diverse Energy Communities (Pilots).
- Solutions prioritize interoperability, scalability, security, and trustworthiness.
- Integrates TSO/ DSO flexibility services, demand response, and dynamic pricing.
- Enhances coordination via dataspace and middleware for
- Decision support algorithms empower better information exchange between consumers and prosumers in energy services.
- Blockchain-based transactions ensure credibility, security, traceability, and engagement.

Consortium

The U2DEMO project brings together 16 consortium partners from 8 countries, including 14 main partners and 2 associated partners. The project coordinates a 5-year Horizon R&D initiative (H2020 ID: 101019147).

Legend:

- Technology Provider
- Utility
- Research center | University
- Industry
- Foundation/ Association
- Municipality
- Services

Portuguese Pilot

- Valverde is a small rural village in the countryside of Evora.
- It has around 450 inhabitants and 200 residential buildings connected to the LV grid.
- Challenges addressed:
 - Integration of P2P trading concept to manage the energy transactions between members of a REC with empirical testing of algorithms for energy sharing.
 - Comparative analysis and assessment of P2P energy sharing mechanisms in contrast to algorithms that do not encompass the P2P mechanism.

Dutch Pilot

- Living Lab Scheveningen is the flagship programme of The Hague's Smart City activities.
- In the lab, a number of societal challenges around environment, safety and sustainability are tackled in the public space.
- Challenges addressed:
 - Open-source technology focussed on decentralised principles.
 - Technologies that focus on privacy protection & security. For example: edge computing, federated learning, wallet-systems and more.
 - The inclusion of grid factors in P2P trading and the test of different services.

Four Phases

- Phase 1: Analysis of existing solutions for P2P trading, Energy Sharing and ECs in European countries and social research (M1-13)
- Phase 2: R&I Development under WP2, WP3 and WP4 (M18-24)
- Phase 3: Prototyping and Demonstration under WPs (M13-39)
- Phase 4: Main conclusions, Guidelines, Roadmap and Recommendations under WP6 (M4)

Four Phases

Phase I: Policies and Business (Methodologies mapping of regulatory, financial and business models; Social Factors and Energy Priority Migration; Feasibility Studies and Call Services Communities Assessment)

Phase II: U2DEMO Platform (Algorithms Development: P2P Trading, Data Analytics, Decision Support, Energy Sharing, Billing and Settlement)

Phase III: Demonstrators (P2P Trading and Energy Sharing; P2P Energy Sharing including Grid Factors and Demand Response (M1) Demo; P2P Energy Sharing including Social Benefits and Flexibility Services (M2) Demo; Call for Demo Realization)

Phase IV: Assessment and Roadmap (Assessment of Open Source Tools; Evaluation of the Proposed ECs; Scalability, replicability and Business Models; Recommendations and guidelines to increase the user engagement in P2P trading and Energy Sharing; Public recommendations and guidelines on the evolution of P2P trading and energy sharing mechanism)

Figure 20 - Project Overview PPT

U2DEMO Minutes of Meeting

Minutes of Meeting

U2DEMO

Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy democratization

Meeting Title:	Meeting Date/Time:
Meeting Coordinator:	Meeting Location:

Attendee Name	Organisation	Present

Meeting Agenda

Meeting Summary

Outline points discussed and state clear outcome for the meeting

This document has been produced in the context of the U2DEMO project. Views and opinions expressed in this document are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission and Environment Executive Agency (EEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

U2DEMO Minutes of Meeting

Decisions taken	
Description	Notes

Actions	
Description	Notes

Proposed Agenda for Next Meeting: Proposed Next Meeting Date:

Related Document	Location

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Figure 21 - Template Minutes of Meeting

The screenshot shows the Overleaf LaTeX editor interface. On the left, the 'Code Editor' displays the following LaTeX source code:

```

1 \renewcommand{\raggedright}{} % Deletes the raggedright modus in the
  whole document
2
3
4 \documentclass{report}
5
6 %% insert the name of the deliverable here
7 \newcommand{\NameDel}{{[Name of Del.]}}
8
9
10
11
12 %% Choose here: either long or short version
13 %\input{Long_version/long_main}
14
15 \input{Short_version/short_main}
16
17

```

The right pane shows the compiled PDF document. The title page includes the following text:

Funded by the European Union
 Horizon Europe
 EUROPEAN COMMISSION
 European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)
 Grant agreement no. 101160684

U2DEMO
Use of open-source P2P energy sharing platforms for energy Democratization

Short Version: Deliverable D xx.x
 TITLE

Authors:
 AUTHORS LINE 1
 AUTHORS LINE 2
 AUTHORS LINE 3

Link to the long version: LINK

Disclaimer
 This document has been produced in the context of the U2DEMO project. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible.

Figure 22 - LaTeX Template, available in Overleaf

News/Event

News and Event Submission Template

U2DEMO

Contact Point Name	Institution	Email

1. Title of the Event or News Article

2. Project Members involved

3. Date of the event

4. Description

5. Image

Please send us attached or a link to the location on the [Sharepoint](#).

Figure 23 - News and Event Submission Template